

APPENDIX – Sources of primary studies identified in the SLR

As for the place of publication, 72.28% (133) of the studies came from Conferences, and others 27.71% (51) came from Journals and Magazines, as detailed below.

Conferences	Primary Studies	(%)
International Conference on Global Software Engineering	44	33,08
International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	10	7,52
International Conference on Software Engineering	8	6,02
Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	8	6,02
International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	4	3,01
Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	4	3,01
International Conference on Requirements Engineering	3	2,26
International Conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement	3	2,26
Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems	3	2,26
Software Engineering Approaches For Offshore and Outsourced Development	3	2,26
Agile Conference	3	2,26
Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2	1,50
Conference on Computer Personnel Research	2	1,50
International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering	2	1,50
International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing	2	1,50
European Conference on Information Systems	2	1,50
International Conference on Computer and Management	1	0,75
International Workshop on Web 2.0 for Software Engineering	1	0,75
International Workshop on Groupware: Design, Implementation, and Use	1	0,75
International Conference on Global Software Engineering Workshops	1	0,75
International Symposium on Collaborative Technologies and Systems	1	0,75
International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction	1	0,75
International Symposium on Management, Engineering and Informatics	1	0,75
International Conference on Information Systems	1	0,75
International Workshop on Recommendation Systems for Software Engineering	1	0,75
International Conference on Open Source Systems	1	0,75
Malaysian Conference in Software Engineering	1	0,75
International Conference on Product Focused Software	1	0,75
International Symposium on Computer and Information Sciences	1	0,75
Conference of The Center for Advanced Studies on Collaborative Research	1	0,75

Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications	1	0,75
International Conference on Collaboration and Technology	1	0,75
International Workshop on Global Sourcing of Information Technology and Business Processes	1	0,75
International Conference on Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming	1	0,75
International Workshop on Intercultural Collaboration	1	0,75
International Conference on Supporting Group Work	1	0,75
International Workshop on Social Software Engineering	1	0,75
On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems Workshops	1	0,75
Conference on Software Maintenance and Reengineering	1	0,75
Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering	1	0,75
Computer Software and Applications Conference	1	0,75
International Conference Companion on Object Oriented Programming Systems Languages and Applications Companion	1	0,75
International Multitopic Conference	1	0,75
India Software Engineering Conference	1	0,75
International Professional Communication Conference	1	0,75
Total	133	100

Journals/Magazine	primary studies	(%)
IEEE Software	5	9,80
Communications Of The ACM	5	9,80
Journal of Software: Evolution And Process	4	7,84
IET Software	4	7,84
Expert Systems	3	5,88
Information Systems Journal	3	5,88
Software Process: Improvement and Practice	2	3,92
Information and Software Technology	2	3,92
Transactions on Professional Communication	2	3,92
Transactions on Software Engineering	2	3,92
SPIE Conference	1	1,96
Journal of Universal Computer Science	1	1,96
Journal of Systems and Software	1	1,96
International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Systems	1	1,96
Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology	1	1,96
International Journal Empirical Software Engineering	1	1,96
Information Technology & People	1	1,96
Electronic Markets	1	1,96
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research	1	1,96
Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference	1	1,96
Requirements Engineering	1	1,96
International Workshop on Global Software Development for the Practitioner	1	1,96
Information Systems Management	1	1,96
International Workshop on Managing Requirements Knowledge	1	1,96
The Computer Journal	1	1,96

Journal of Information Technology	1	1,96
Conferences on Advances in New Technologies, Interactive Interfaces and Communicability	1	1,96
International Journal of Information and Communication Engineering	1	1,96
International Journal of Project Management	1	1,96
Total	51	100